

Synthesis and Biological Activities of 2-Aryl-3-(3-methyl-1,2-benzisoxazol-6-oxylamino)thiazolidin-4-ones

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Thiazolidinones¹ and benzisoxazoles² possess various biological activities. This prompted us to undertake the syntheses of a series of 2-aryl-3-(3-methyl-1,2-benzisoxazol-6-oxylamino)thiazolidin-4-ones.

6-Hydroxy-3-methyl-1,2-benzisoxazole (1) was reacted with ClCH_2COOH , yielding 2. The ester of 2 was converted to the hydrazide (3). Condensation of 3 with substituted aromatic aldehydes gave the corresponding Schiff bases (4). Thiazolidinones (5a-k) were obtained from 4 by reacting with thioglycolic acid (Scheme 1).

Results and Discussion

The compounds did not exhibit any oedema inhibiting activity. Compound 5a also did not show any chronic inflammation inhibiting activity. Compounds 5a-k failed to protect rats from electrically induced seizures as also from convulsions induced by pentylenetetrazol. Thus the compounds were found to be devoid of any anti-inflammatory and anticonvulsant activities. 5a-k showed no inhibitory activity on *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Corynebacterium diphtheriae*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Escherichia coli*. No activity was seen against the fungus *Candida albicans*. 5a-e were found to inhibit the human strain H₃₇R_v of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* at 100 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ concentration. The rest of the compounds were found to be inactive. Table I shows the antitubercular activity data of 5a-k.

Although no conclusive structure-activity relationship has emerged from the antitubercular screening, it appears that the 2-aryl substituent

plays some role in determining the activity of the compound. The active ones (5a-e) have a phenyl, *p*-chlorophenyl, *o*-chlorophenyl, *p*-nitrophenyl and

Scheme 1

m-nitrophenyl as the 2-aryl substituent. It was surprising to find that **5h** with a 2,4-dichloro substitution in the phenyl ring is less active compared to **5b** or **5c**. At this stage it is rather difficult to hypothesise on the relative influence of the benzisoxazole or the thiazolidinone moiety on the activity of the compounds.

Experimental

M.p.s. were determined using open capillaries and are uncorrected. The purity of the samples were checked by running tlc on silica gel plates. Ir spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer and pmr spectra on a Varian (60 MHz) spectrometer.

3-Methyl-1,2-benzisoxazol-6-oxyacetic acid (2): To **1** (0.08 mol), dissolved in KOH (33% : 33 ml), was added a solution of ClCH₂COOH (50% ; 24 ml), and the mixture was cooled in ice for 45 min and refluxed for 12 h. It was then cooled, acidified with dilute HCl. The resulting solid was stirred with a saturated solution of NaHCO₃ and filtered. Acidification of the filtrate gave **2** which was crystallised from hot water, (55%), m.p. 156–57°.

3-Methyl-1,2-benzisoxazol-6-oxyacetic acid hydrazide (3): Compound **2** was esterified by the standard procedure, and the ethyl ester (0.038 mol) in EtOH, was vigorously shaken with hydrazine hydrate (0.05 mol) for 10 min. The resulting solid was crystallised from EtOH, (70%), m.p. 187°.

The hydrazones (4): Compound **3** (0.01 mol) was refluxed with suitably substituted aromatic aldehyde (0.01 mol) in EtOH containing catalytic amounts of HOAc. The hydrazone (Schiff base) separated as a yellow solid within 10 min in the reaction flask, was crystallised from EtOH as yellow needles.

TABLE I—PHYSICAL AND ANTITUBERCULAR ACTIVITY* DATA OF COMPOUNDS 5a–k

Compd. no.	Ar	M.p. °C	Yield %	Concentration (μg ml ⁻¹)		
				100	10	Control
5a	Phenyl	83	45	—	+	++
b	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	98	35	—	+	++
c	<i>o</i> -Chlorophenyl	172	30	—	+	++
d	<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl	145	35	—	+	++
e	<i>m</i> -Nitrophenyl	101	25	—	+	++
f	<i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl	189	25	++	++	++
g	3,4-Dichlorophenyl	145	30	++	++	+++
h	2,4-Dichlorophenyl	160	50	+	++	+++
i	<i>p</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	170	10	+	++	+++
j	<i>p</i> -Methylphenyl	95	45	+	++	+++
k	3,4-Methylene-dioxyphenyl	140	40	+	++	+++

(—) ≡ denotes no growth; (+) ≡ less than 20 colonies; (++) ≡ more than 20 colonies; (+++) ≡ confluent growth.

*Streptomycin showed inhibitory activity at 100 μg ml⁻¹.

2 Aryl-3-(3-methyl-1,2-benzisoxazol-6-oxyacetylamino)thiazolidin-4-ones (5): A mixture of **4** (0.01 mol) and HSCH₂COOH (0.01 mol) was refluxed in

dry benzene (50 ml) with arrangement of separation of water by a Dean-Stark apparatus. At the end of the reaction as indicated by a clear distillate, the solvent was removed under reduced pressure and the residue stirred with a saturated solution of NaHCO₃ to remove any unreacted HSCH₂COOH. The solid that separated was crystallised from EtOH (Table I): ν_{\max} (nujol) 3 250, (NH), 1 730 (ring C=O) 1 690 (NHCO), 1 620 (C=N) and 1 280 cm⁻¹ (C—O—C); δ (DMSO-d₆) 8.9 (1H, s, NH), 7.5–6.9 (8H, ArH), 5.73 (1H, s, CH), 4.56 (2H, s, O—CH₂CO), 3.7 (2H, s, S—CH₂CO) and 2.43 (3H, CH₃).

Biological activities: Anti-inflammatory, anti-convulsant, antibacterial and antitubercular screenings were done on compounds 5a–k. Anti-inflammatory screening was done using the carrageenan paw oedema model³ in rats for acute inflammation. Cotton pellet granuloma method⁴ was employed as the model for chronic inflammation. The electrically induced seizures⁵ and pentylenetetrazol induced convulsions⁶ were produced in rats to test for anticonvulsant activity. Antibacterial activity was screened⁷ against *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Corynebacterium diphtheriae*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Escherichia coli* and antifungal activity against *Candida albicans*. Antitubercular activity was studied by observing the growth pattern of the human strain H₃₇R_v of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* in LJ medium in the presence of the test compounds⁸.

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